

Lymphocytes and monocytes undergo swift suppression of IL-10R, IL-6R, and IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ signaling under high concentrations of different cytokines

Maxim Kuznetsov^{1,*}, Joao Rodrigues Lima Junior², Russell C. Rockne¹,
Sergio Branciamore^{1,†}, Andrei S. Rodin^{1,†}, Peter P. Lee^{2,†}

¹Department of Computational and Quantitative Medicine,
Beckman Research Institute of City of Hope, Duarte, CA, 91010 USA

²Department of Immuno-Oncology,
Beckman Research Institute of City of Hope, Duarte, CA, 91010 USA

*Corresponding author: kouznetsovmb@gmail.com

†Co-corresponding authors: sbranciamore@coh.org, arodin@coh.org, plee@coh.org

Abstract

The JAK-STAT signaling pathway is fundamental for immune system regulation. It involves phosphorylation of several types of STAT proteins in response to binding of cytokines to immune cell receptors. Traditionally, the immune signaling studies focus on measuring the levels of phosphorylated STATs (pSTATs) following individual cytokine application. We developed an experimental approach, based on multiparametric flow cytometry, to simultaneously measure the levels of five pSTATs after 15 minutes of cell treatment with high doses of individual cytokines and their paired combinations.

Analysis of our experimental data involving peripheral blood mononuclear cells from healthy donors reveals systematic suppression of IL-10R, IL-6R, and IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ signaling in T cells, B cells, NK cells, and monocytes. This suppression is mediated by at least all tested cytokines that do not induce relevant pSTATs by themselves. Remarkably, the cytokines with negligible own signaling do act as prominent selective signaling suppressors. In contrast, the signaling of IFNAR, IFNGR, IL-4R, and IL-2R $\alpha\beta\gamma$ remains largely unaffected by co-application of other cytokines.

We propose that this pattern of signaling suppression represents an evolutionary developed mechanism enhancing the promptness, specialization, and efficiency of the immune response, while increased concentration of cytokines serves as a danger signal of inefficient response. We hypothesize that selective signaling suppression arises from the differential sensitivity of conformations of cytokine-receptor complexes to the increase of cell surface tension and stiffness, which is caused by effects following the binding of cytokines to membrane-associated molecules, including glycocalyx elements. While the rewiring of immune cell signaling should represent a powerful evolutionary tool for augmentation of adaptive response, it should also lead to the prolonged suppression of counteracting signaling pathways, culminating in cytokine release syndrome and contributing to autoimmune diseases.

Introduction

One of the crucial components of immune cell signaling is the JAK-STAT pathway, which depends on interactions between Janus kinases (JAKs) with signal transducer and activator of transcription proteins (STATs)¹. JAK-STAT pathway promotes cell proliferation, differentiation, migration, and apoptosis, playing a key role in the immune system development and balance. In mammals, it serves as the primary signaling mechanism for numerous cytokines and growth factors². Their binding to different receptors, associated with common intracellular JAKs, alters receptor configurations bringing JAKs into close proximity. In this arrangement, JAKs phosphorylate tyrosine residues on each other and on the receptor, enabling STAT proteins to bind to the receptor and undergo phosphorylation. Phosphorylated STATs, or pSTATs, detach from the receptors, dimerize, and enter the nucleus to trigger transcription of target genes, leading to production of new receptors and cytokines, as well as to other downstream effects³.

The JAK-STAT pathway is highly conserved across species from drosophila⁴ to mammals, with structurally similar core components underscoring its evolutionary significance^{5,6}. Its signaling is modulated by a variety of regulatory proteins, including suppressors of cytokine signaling (SOCSs), protein inhibitors of activated STATs, and protein tyrosine phosphatases⁷. Dysregulation of JAK-STAT signaling can result in various autoimmune diseases, leukemias, and weakened immune responses^{2,6,8}. Notably, during the recent COVID-19 pandemic, the involvement of JAK-STAT pathway was highlighted as a central regulator of hyperinflammation in critically ill patients⁹.

The major significance of JAK-STAT pathway in immune cells promotes its experimental investigation, with relevant studies focusing both on the early stages of pathway activation by performing measurements of various pSTATs^{10–13}, and on the downstream functional outcomes of cytokine administration^{14–16}. Most of the studies on JAK-STAT signaling concentrate either on application of individual cytokines^{12,13,15,16} or combined administration of cytokines without comparing the outcomes to individual cytokine effects^{10,11}. While several earlier studies explored in detail the phenomena resulting from specific pairs of co-administered cytokines^{17–20}, such research has become infrequent lately²¹.

However, it is well known that in physiological conditions, cellular behavior is shaped by simultaneous and context-dependent action of multiple cytokines. Some cytokines can exert opposing pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory effects depending on cell type, timing, dosing, and interactions with other cytokines. Therefore, many cytokines are termed pleiotropic, and their effects are often described as ambiguous^{22–24}. Similarly, the immune system as a whole can be both protective and harmful to the host. These contradictory effects stem at least in part from the immune system’s need to recognize and respond to a wide variety of threats. To ensure an efficient response, evolution has shaped several interconnected yet inevitably conflicting strategies, each relying on JAK-STAT signaling. The three major types of immune responses are type 1 response, targeting intracellular microbes and abnormal host cells; type 2 response, protecting the body from parasites and allergens; and type 3 response, combating extracellular bacteria and fungi²⁵. While these strategies may incur severe side effects for certain individuals, the specialization and adaptability of immune system are of paramount importance for the overall survival of the species²⁶.

Motivated by the pleiotropism of cytokine roles, we developed an experimental approach using multiparametric flow cytometry to analyze the effects of individual cytokines and cytokine pairs on immune cells derived from the peripheral blood of healthy human donors (thus representing a healthy baseline immune signaling system). Our methodology enables simultaneous measurement of five STAT types, focusing on short-term immune cell responses with cytokine treatment limited to 15 minutes. This time frame minimizes the influence of newly transcribed cytokines and receptors on the experimental outcomes. Our experimental data reveals the systematic suppression of JAK-STAT signaling of certain cytokine-receptor complexes in T cells, B cells, NK cells, and monocytes. In this paper, we dissect these suppression patterns, propose their evolutionary roles, and put forward a mechanistic hypothesis for the systematic signaling suppression.

Results

Immune cell pSTATome is cell type-specific

In the first experimental setting, we investigated the effects of eight individually applied cytokines on the phosphorylation levels of five STATs across immune cells in absence of activating factors: T cells (Figure 1A), monocytes (Figure 1B), B cells (Figure 1C), and natural killer (NK) cells (Figure 1D). The immune cells were obtained from nineteen donors, with an equal number of cells from each donor selected for every setting in the presented aggregate analysis. Cytokines were administered at 50 ng/mL dose each, except for IFN- α which dose was 1000 IU/mL. Cytokine effects were quantified using the Cumulative Shift Index (CSI), based on rank-biserial correlation for Mann–Whitney U test (see Materials and Methods). The CSI value of 1 or -1 would correspond to non-overlapping distributions, while its values near 0 indicate minor shifts. To ensure robust analysis, we consider only the shifts with $|\text{CSI}| \geq 0.1$ and p-values < 0.001 as significant.

The results consistently reproduce the canonical signaling axes. IL-10/STAT3 and IL-4/STAT6 signaling are prominent in all the considered cell types and their identified subtypes (Figure S1A), and for each donor (Figure S1B). In certain cell types, these dominant signaling axes are complemented by moderate phosphorylation of additional STATs. In particular, IL-10/STAT1 signaling is evident in classical and non-classical monocytes, as well as in memory B cells.

Less abundant signaling, varying across donors, and restricted to specific cell types, is induced by IFN- γ , IL-2, and IL-6. The primary IFN- γ effect is pSTAT1 signaling, not detected in resting NK cells; IL-2 induces STAT5 in T cells and NK cells; and IL-6 phosphorylates STAT3 in classical monocytes and T cells. In certain cell types, the signaling profiles of these cytokines are as well supplemented by moderate induction of other pSTATs.

IFN- α demonstrates the most diverse action. Our experimental panel did not include an antibody for pSTAT2, which has a narrow activity profile and functions primarily as a part of a heterodimer with pSTAT1²⁷. Literature provides direct evidence that IFN- α phosphorylates STAT2 in T cells²⁸ and B cells²⁹. Thus, we can conclude that IFN- α induces phosphorylation of every STAT in adaptive immune cells. However, in monocytes it has no significant effect on STAT6, which is notably expressed in these cells, as evidenced by IL-4 signaling in them. Additionally, classical monocytes do not exhibit IFN- α /STAT4 signaling, which should stem from the negligible levels of STAT4 in resting monocytes³⁰.

IL-12 shows only weak activity within 15-minute treatment, likely due to the scarcity of functional IL-12 receptors in resting T cells, B cells³¹, and monocytes³⁰. As a true negative control, TGF- β shows no significant signaling at the aggregate level, which is consistent with the lack of literature evidence supporting its involvement in JAK-STAT signaling of immune cells¹². We have previously shown that TGF- β also induces minimal signaling through its canonical pathway in this experimental setting³². This aligns with other reports showing modest TGF- β signaling and low expression of its signaling components in resting lymphocytes^{33,34} and monocytes³⁵.

Figure 1: Effects of individual cytokines on STATs phosphorylation. Cytokines were applied for 15 minutes to the immune cells from nineteen healthy donors: **A)** T cells, **B)** monocytes, **C)** B cells, **D)** natural killer (NK) cells. Colored cells in the tables indicate significant stimulation or inhibition of specific pSTATs, with all corresponding p-values being less than 0.001 (Mann–Whitney U test). Effect strength is quantified by Cumulative Shift Index (CSI), based on rank-biserial correlation for Mann–Whitney U test. Distributions of pSTAT levels in untreated and treated cells are shown for eight specified settings. Here and further each cytokine was applied at 50 ng/mL dose, except for IFN- α which dose was 1000 IU/mL; cell counts are provided in the supplementary Excel (.xlsx) files.

We observe several additional effects at the aggregate level, where cells display reduced pSTAT concentrations after treatment. Inhibition of pSTAT3 levels by IL-2 in NK cells and monocytes may result from the selective formation of pSTAT3:pSTAT5 heterodimers³⁶, interfering with pSTAT3 binding to the assay antibodies. Downregulation of pSTAT4 by IL-12 in classical monocytes is less noteworthy due to the negligible expression of both IL-12Rs and STAT4 in their basal state³⁰.

Overall, these results align with and expand upon the recent studies exploring short-term effects of individual cytokine applications in human immune cells across more limited cell type repertoires^{12,13}.

IL-10, IL-6 and IL-2 signaling is systematically suppressed by other cytokines

Concurrently with the above experiments, we performed paired administration of the same doses of IL-10 in conjunction with other cytokines to the immune cells from the same donors. The results reveal notable suppression of IL-10/STAT3 signaling by different cytokines across all the considered cell types: T cells (Figure 2A), monocytes (Figure 2B), B cells (Figure 2C), and NK cells (Figure 2D), as well as in all of their identified subtypes (Figure S2A). Additionally, we observe suppression of IL-10/STAT1 signaling in both types of monocytes and memory B cells, where this axis is prominent. To quantify these effects, we introduce the Level of Suppression metric (LoS, see Materials and Methods), which takes values from 0 if no significant suppression is observed to 1 if the pSTAT distribution of cells treated with two cytokines matches that of untreated cells.

Figure 2: Effects of paired conjunction of IL-10 with other cytokines on STATs phosphorylation. Cytokines were applied for 15 minutes to the immune cells from nineteen healthy donors: **A)** T cells, **B)** monocytes, **C)** B cells, **D)** NK cells. Orange cells in the tables represent suppression of IL-10 signaling by a co-applied cytokine. Purple cells indicate suppression of a co-applied cytokine signaling by IL-10. The suppression of cytokine *a* by cytokine *b* is highlighted only for the cases where $CSI(Base \rightarrow a) \geq 0.1$ with $p < 0.001$ and $-CSI(a \rightarrow ab) \geq 0.05$ with $p < 0.001$. Level of Suppression (LoS) is evaluated as $LoS(a|b) = -CSI(a \rightarrow ab)/CSI(Base \rightarrow a)$. Gray cells denote the settings where neither of two cytokines induces the relevant pSTAT significantly, both related p-values being ≥ 0.001 . Yellow cells highlight the settings where both cytokines significantly induce the relevant pSTAT, interfering with potential detection of suppression. Distributions of pSTAT levels in untreated and treated cells are shown for four settings.

Detection of IL-10 signaling suppression by IFN- α and IL-6 is not always feasible, since a reduction in the levels of pSTAT3 can be compensated by its supplemental induction. Nevertheless, suppression of IL-10 signaling by IFN- α is evident in both types of monocytes and several T cell subsets, while suppressive action of IL-6 is detected in all cell types where IL-6/STAT3 signaling is negligible, and also in several cell types where it is prominent: classical monocytes, memory B cells, and several T cell subtypes.

Across all the studied settings, TGF- β and IL-12 emerge as the most potent suppressors of IL-10 activity, despite displaying negligible or weak JAK-STAT signaling by themselves. The level of suppression notably varies among donors, with some of them exhibiting weaker signaling suppression in most settings (Figure S2B).

Our results also show that IL-10 can interfere with the effects of other cytokines. IL-2/STAT5 signaling is significantly suppressed by IL-10 in almost all cells where this axis is prominent: T cells, the majority of their isolated subtypes, and NK cells. IFN- α /STAT6 signaling is slightly suppressed in naive and memory B cells, but the phosphorylation of other STATs induced by IFN- α remains unaffected by IL-10 across all studied cell types. In contrast, this aggregate analysis

shows no evidence of IL-10-induced suppression of IL-4 and IFN- γ signaling.

These findings motivated us to conduct additional experiments focused on different cytokine pairs. The detailed aggregate and individual donor analyses for all cell types and their identified subtypes are provided in supplementary materials for combinations involving IL-2 (Figure S3), IL-6 (Figure S4), IL-4 (Figure S5), and IFN- α (Figure S6).

Figure 3: Effects of paired conjunction of cytokines on STATs phosphorylation. Cytokines were applied for 15 minutes to the immune cells from the groups of five healthy donors each: **A**) IL-2, **B**) IL-6, **C**) IL-4, **D**) IFN- α (main cytokines) in paired conjunction with other cytokines. Orange cells in the tables represent suppression of main cytokine signaling by a co-applied cytokine. The suppression of cytokine a by cytokine b is highlighted only for the cases where $\text{CSI}(\text{Base} \rightarrow a) \geq 0.1$ with $p < 0.001$ and $-\text{CSI}(a \rightarrow ab) \geq 0.05$ with $p < 0.001$. Gray cells denote the cases where the main cytokine does not induce the relevant pSTAT significantly ($p \geq 0.001$). Distributions of pSTAT levels in untreated and treated cells are shown for three specified settings.

The induction of pSTAT5 by IL-2 in T cells and NK cells is suppressed by each co-administered cytokine, except IFN- α , which induces pSTAT5 by itself (Figure 3A). Co-application of IL-4 shows the weakest but statistically significant suppression of IL-2/STAT5 signaling in T cells, with CSI = -0.04, which formally falls below our stringent detection threshold. In CD8+ TEMRA cells of two donors, IL-2 also induces pSTAT3, which is as well suppressed by all cytokines not signaling through it.

However, IL-2/STAT5 signaling is remarkably robust in each of the identified subtypes of regulatory T cells (Tregs). At the individual donor level, we detect only two related instances of suppression in Tregs. Intriguingly, resting T cells and NK cells express the intermediate-affinity form of IL-2 receptor (IL-2R $\beta\gamma$), while Tregs are known to express its high-affinity form (IL-2R $\alpha\beta\gamma$)³⁷.

IL-6/STAT3 signaling in T cells and classical monocytes is suppressed by all co-applied cytokines, which do not induce pSTAT3 in corresponding cells (Figure 3B). This effect is consistently detected across all T cell subtypes that exhibit IL-6 signaling. In contrast, IL-4 induces pSTAT6 robustly in all considered cell types (Figure 3C). Only one donor exhibits consistent, but weak, suppression of IL-4/STAT6 signaling by each co-administered cytokine, except IFN- α , within a single cell type (NK cells). In this assay, we also performed co-treatment of cells with IL-10 and IL-4, which reproduced the previously observed outcome – IL-10 signaling was suppressed across all cell types, while IL-4 signaling was largely unaffected by IL-10 (Figure S5A).

The multifaceted signaling of IFN- α is largely resistant to the co-administered cytokines (Figure 3D). At the aggregate level, the only observed suppression events involve IFN- α /STAT6 axis in classical monocytes, naive B cells, and effector memory T cells; IFN- α /STAT1 axis in NK cells and CD8+ TEMRA cells; and IFN- α /STAT3 axis in NK cells.

Suppressive power of cytokines rarely depends on their signaling level

Direct comparison of the signaling suppression levels shows that IL-10/STAT3 signaling undergoes stronger suppression by IFN- γ in monocytes than lymphocytes (Figure 4A). This correlates with the higher levels of IFN- γ /STAT1 signaling in monocytes and happens despite the fact that IFN- γ by itself significantly induces pSTAT3 in monocytes, complementing the action of IL-10. In contrast, for four other cytokines that do not typically induce pSTAT3, IL-10/STAT3 suppression levels are similar in monocytes and lymphocytes.

Figure 4: IFN- γ signaling correlates with IL-10/STAT3 signaling suppression. **A**) Comparison of signaling intensities (CSI) of IL-2, IL-4, IFN- γ , IL-12, and TGF- β alongside the levels of IL-10/STAT3 signaling suppression (LoS) in lymphocytes and monocytes. The average CSI and LoS values for twenty individual donors were aggregated from classical and non-classical monocytes (M) and eleven distinct types of lymphocytes (L): NK cells; memory and naive B cells; naive, central memory, TEMRA, and effector memory CD4+ T cells; and equivalent subtypes of CD8+ T cells. The p-values were estimated by the Mann–Whitney U test. **B**) Scatter plot of IFN- γ -induced suppression of IL-10/STAT3 signaling and the intensities of IFN- γ /STAT1 and IL-10/STAT3 signaling in naive B cells from twenty healthy donors. Coefficients of partial correlation between suppression levels and the intensity of each of the two axes while controlling for the intensity of another axis, ρ , and corresponding p-values were estimated by Spearman’s rank test. Among all the cell types and signaling axes of cytokines co-administered with IL-10 (IL-2/STAT5, IL-4/STAT6, IL-6/STAT3, IFN- γ /STAT1, and five IFN- α axes), this is the only setting showing a statistically significant partial correlation between the levels of co-applied cytokine signaling and IL-10/STAT3 suppression.

We also examined the relationships between the levels of cytokines' signaling and IL-10/STAT3 suppression at the cell type-level using individual donor data. However, innate immune cells, and to a lesser extent CD4+ T cells, showed significant correlations between the signaling levels of different cytokines (with the notable exception of IL-2/STAT5 axis), which interfered with the task of isolating the separate influence of cytokine signaling on IL-10/STAT3 suppression (Table S1). In contrast, B cells and CD8+ T cells exhibited more heterogeneous signaling patterns, possibly reflecting their more specialized roles in the immune system.

Overall, IFN- γ emerged as the only cytokine with significant partial correlation between its signaling and induced IL-10/STAT3 suppression within a single cell type, naive B cells (Figure 4B). For all other cytokines, we found no evidence of correlation between their signaling intensities and suppressive capabilities.

Discussion

Common pro-inflammatory effects of IL-10 are unlikely due to its direct action

As our experimental data suggests, sufficiently elevated cytokine concentrations should lead to the observed pattern of rewiring of lymphocyte and monocyte signaling in humans. We hypothesize that this rewiring serves to mobilize immune resources and enhance the efficiency of immune response, while abnormally high cytokine levels serve as a "danger signal" of the currently inefficient response.

IL-10 is recognized as a key anti-inflammatory cytokine³⁸, one of its functions being reflected in its original name, "cytokine synthesis inhibitory factor"³⁹. Its functions include promotion of B cell apoptosis upon activation⁴⁰, inhibition of NK cell responses⁴¹, and suppression of T cell activation which IL-10 can induce both directly, by mitigating T cell receptor signaling⁴², and indirectly, by reducing the antigen-presenting capacity of monocytes⁴³ and preventing dendritic cell maturation⁴⁴ (Table S2⁴⁵⁻⁵⁰). Thus, the nature of effects induced by IL-10 strongly suggests that the suppression of its signaling should augment the immune response.

However, multiple *in vitro*⁵¹⁻⁵⁷ and *in vivo*⁵⁸⁻⁶³ experimental studies, along with several clinical investigations⁶⁴⁻⁶⁸, provide evidence of the immunostimulatory effects associated with the high-dose IL-10 administration (Table S3). In *in vitro* experiments, these effects emerge upon immune cell activation after hours or days of IL-10 pre-treatment and include enhanced T cell survival⁵¹, increased production of cytotoxic mediators⁵⁹ and cytokines⁵² by T cells, amplified B cell proliferation and antibody secretion⁵³, and heightened NK cell cytotoxicity^{54,55}. Several studies explicitly demonstrate the dose-dependent nature of these effects, with their intensity saturating within an IL-10 dose range of ~30-1000 ng/mL^{53-55,59}. *In vivo* and clinical studies corroborate these findings, demonstrating enhanced activation of T cells and NK cells^{59,63,66,67}, and their intensified tumor infiltration^{58,59,62,66} under high dose IL-10 administration. In accordance with these findings, during the recent COVID-19 pandemic, high IL-10 level was identified as a predictor of severe disease progression⁶⁹, associated with a high proportion of hyperactivated T cells in the peripheral blood⁷⁰.

Our findings challenge the prevailing notion that these phenomena represent direct pro-inflammatory effects of IL-10⁷¹. Recently, Islam et al.⁷² proposed that the inability of IL-10 to exert its anti-inflammatory effects during a cytokine storm may arise from the resistance or hyporesponsiveness of activated immune cells to it. Our results support this hypothesis and further suggest that the immune cell hyporesponsiveness to IL-10 represents a direct consequence of elevated cytokine levels. Notably, experimental data of Prince et al.⁷³ show that cytokine levels in tissues, when combined together, can reach more than 75 ng/g in a mouse model of chronic infection which, when benchmarked against our dosing regime, highlights the feasibility of selective signaling suppression in immune cells within inflamed tissues.

We further hypothesize that the aforementioned immunostimulatory effects are not only facilitated by IL-10 signaling suppression but also represent a biomechanical response of immune cells to abnormally high cytokine levels. Currently, physical forces are increasingly recognized as important immunity modulators, with alterations in tissue mechanics being acknowledged as the danger signal alerting immune cells to potential injury or infection⁷⁴. In particular, a physiologically realistic increase of substrate stiffness enhances activation of NK cells⁷⁵ and macrophages⁷⁶, induces the accumulation of BCR molecules in the immunological synapses of B cells⁷⁷, and elevates T cell cytokine production⁷⁸ and proliferation rate, while lowering the threshold dose of antigen required to induce T cell effector responses⁷⁹. Thus, mechanosensing serves as an important part of immune cell activation process. Therefore, it seems plausible that sufficiently high cytokine levels may as well enhance immune cell responsiveness via biomechanical effects.

Recent studies highlight another immunostimulatory function of IL-10, which is the prevention of activation-induced T cell exhaustion^{80,81}. While this effect may not completely align with the classical paradigm of anti-inflammatory role of IL-10, it is consistent with its characterization as a suppressor of immune cell activity⁸², which encompasses its primary functions under normal physiological concentrations (Table S2).

Suppression of IL-6 signaling should facilitate adaptive immune response

IL-6 is a crucial driver of the acute immune response. In reaction to infections and tissue injuries, IL-6 is produced by macrophages⁸³ to stimulate secretion of acute phase proteins by the liver. These proteins include serum amyloid A,

a key promoter of type 3 immune response against extracellular bacteria and fungi, eliminated by innate immune cells.

Another role of IL-6 is facilitating the transition of immune response to a chronic stage, where eradication of pathogens relies on adaptive immune cells. In particular, IL-6 induces CD4+ T cell secretion of IL-4⁸⁴, which plays a pivotal role in orchestrating type 2 response against parasites and allergens. IL-4 promotes migration of eosinophils⁸⁵ that kill pathogenic targets and mediates recognition of targets by eosinophils via inducing B cell secretion of pathogen-specific IgE antibodies⁸⁶.

Upon another major type of threat – viral infection – various virus-sensing immune cells secrete IFN- α ⁸⁷, which establishes the foundation for type 1 response against intracellular microbes. In particular, IFN- α activates dendritic cells (DCs)⁸⁸ and NK cells⁸⁹, enhances the antigen-presenting function of monocytes⁹⁰, lowers the activation threshold of B cells⁹¹, and promotes proliferation and cytotoxicity of CD8+ T cells⁹², the primary killers of infected cells. Furthermore, IFN- α induces T cell secretion of IFN- γ , which reinforces type 1 response by driving DC maturation⁹³, boosting CD8+ T cells cytotoxicity and motility⁹⁴, and promoting differentiation of monocytes into phagocytic macrophages⁹⁵.

The effects of IL-6, IL-4, IFN- α , and IFN- γ interact in complex ways, reflecting the evolutionarily shaped strategies of the immune system to tailor the distribution of its resources for recognizing and combating a specific type of pathogen while minimizing the damage to healthy cells (Table S2^{96–113}). Some of the effects of different cytokines, such as the IL-6-induced transition to a chronic stage, have complementary nature. Intriguingly, the diverse JAK-STAT signaling of IFN- α , marked by strong induction of pSTAT1 (main factor activated by IFN- γ) and moderate phosphorylation of STAT6 (main factor activated by IL-4), suggests that IFN- α actually fosters an initial broad type of response to be further stratified by more specialized cytokines. Experimental findings of Eriksen et al.¹¹⁴ support this idea, showing that IFN- α induces a time-dependent effect in human T cells, lowering the threshold for IL-4-mediated STAT6 activation during the first 6 hours of administration, and inhibiting IL-4 signaling at longer time frames.

Nevertheless, the effects of different cytokines often inevitably conflict with each other (Table S2). For example, IL-4 inhibits expansion and migration of neutrophils¹¹⁵, interfering with their IL-6-mediated effector functions. IFN- γ enhances activation and cytotoxicity of macrophages¹¹⁶, while IL-6 and IL-4 on contrary promote their regulatory polarization for the resolution of inflammation^{117,118}. Additionally, IL-6, IL-4, and IFN- γ drive different polarization of helper T cells^{119–121} and B cells⁸⁶ to fine-tune their functions for specific types of response. Furthermore, IL-6 suppresses NK cell cytotoxicity¹²² and DC maturation¹²³, and also diverts CD8+ T cells from their crucial cytotoxic role by promoting their differentiation into regulatory cells¹²⁴ and B helper CD8+ T cells¹²⁵.

Thus, despite the essential role of IL-6 in initiating the chronic stage of immune response, its effects can be largely detrimental to the established type 2 and type 1 responses, which combat pathogens not recognized by the innate immunity. This reasoning is supported by clinical data, as inhibition of IL-2 and IFN- γ production by IL-6 was identified as a potential factor mitigating immune system performance during viral infections¹²⁶. Experimental studies further demonstrate that IL-6 can decrease cytotoxicity of NK cells¹²² and monocytes¹²⁷, restrain activation of CD8+ T cells¹²⁸, and inhibit type 1 response-associated differentiation of CD4+ T cells¹²⁹. Therefore, suppression of IL-6 signaling should represent an effective evolutionary mechanism for the optimization of adaptive immune response (Figure 5A).

Consistent with our aforementioned hypothesis on the existence of immunostimulatory effects driven by abnormally elevated levels of various cytokines, several experimental studies with high doses of IL-6 and IL-4 show immunostimulatory outcomes, mainly associated with the augmentation of type 1 response. In particular, in mice, injection of 10 μ g of IL-4 induced production of IFN- γ by NK cells within several hours¹³⁰. In *in vitro* studies, a 6-day treatment of NK cells with 250 ng/mL of IL-6 significantly enhanced their expression of activation antigens¹³¹, a 4-day treatment of cytotoxic T-cells with 5–40 ng/mL of IL-6 promoted their proliferation and inhibited viral replication in a dose-dependent manner¹³², and 24-hour treatment of monocytes with 50–100 ng/mL of IL-6 suppressed the efficacy of their type 3-associated response against fungal pathogens¹³³. Similarly, type 1 response-associated upregulation of IFN- γ production was reported in experimental and clinical studies involving high-dose IL-10 administration^{52,54,59,64,66,67}. These data overall suggest that under abnormally high cytokine levels immune cells not only undergo selective suppression of their signaling but also prioritize enhancement of type 1 response, aiming at rapidly proliferating microbes and thus requiring a swift mobilization of resources to address the critical risk.

Transient suppression of IL-2 should optimize generation of specialized subpopulations

IL-2 is a crucial amplifier of lymphocyte activity (Table S2^{134–137}). It drives clonal expansion and differentiation of T cells¹³⁸; stimulates proliferation, activation, and cytotoxicity of NK cells^{139,140}; and promotes B cell proliferation and differentiation¹⁴¹. Additionally, IL-2 regulates the homeostasis of Tregs which prevent excessive immune reactions¹⁴².

Multiple experimental studies demonstrate activating effects of IL-2 on monocytes which, as our results show, exhibit negligible or very weak IL-2/STAT5 signaling. These studies involve high concentrations of IL-2 and report immunostimulatory effects^{143–146}, some of which vanish at physiological IL-2 levels^{147–150}. Therefore, we propose that these effects also reflect the immune cell reaction to abnormally high concentrations of cytokines, rather than represent consequences of direct IL-2 signaling. Thus, our findings highlight the need for revisiting the IL-2-induced effects in monocytes, as well as in macrophages^{147,151,152}.

Figure 5: Hypothetical explanation of the observed selective suppression of cytokine signaling. A) Potential evolutionary reasons. Under abnormally high concentration of cytokines, serving as a danger signal of inefficient immune response, selective suppression of IL-10-induced inhibition of immune activity and IL-6-driven augmentation of type 3 response should enable mobilization of immune resources towards adaptive response addressing a critical risk. Differential suppressibility of IL-2 receptor forms should allow alleviating proliferative competition between immune cells, fostering proliferation of antigen-experienced rather than naive cells. **B)** Potential biomechanical reasons. Non-specific binding of cytokines to syndecans may induce actin polymerization, while cytokine binding to any membrane-associated molecules should increase steric pressure generated by their crowding. Both effects would result in deformations of cell plasma membrane and in increase of its tension. Structures of cytokine–receptor complexes may govern their differential sensitivity to membrane tension increase and thus yield their selective disruption. This effect should be intensified by the positive feedback mechanism amplifying membrane tension and stiffness.

A distinctive feature of IL-2 signaling is the existence of two forms of its receptor that utilize the same signaling machinery but differ in their binding affinities to IL-2¹⁵³. Resting lymphocytes mainly express intermediate-affinity IL-2R $\beta\gamma$, while high-affinity IL-2R $\alpha\beta\gamma$ ¹⁵⁴ is prominent on activated T cells³⁷ and NK cells¹⁵⁵, as well as on certain subsets of activated B cells¹⁵⁶. The explanations rationalizing the presence of two IL-2R forms generally focus on fine-tuning the sensitivity of different cells to IL-2¹⁵⁷ and on competition for IL-2 among receptors sharing the common gamma chain subunit³⁷. However, these explanations do not address the reasons why differential IL-2 signaling relies on the modification of receptor rather than the regulation of its expression, which is a more straightforward and common evolutionary strategy – in particular, used for the enhancement of IFN- γ signaling in immune cells during type 1 response¹⁵⁸.

The study by Waters et al.¹⁵⁹ aimed to explore potential differences in IL-2 signaling through its two receptor forms. For that purpose, activated human T cells were incubated with or without IL-2R α antibody daclizumab. This antibody was used at concentrations achievable in blood under clinical dosing, which are 15-30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ¹⁶⁰, resulting in $\geq 10^6$ molecules of daclizumab per each of the initial $\sim 10^4$ T cells. The kinetics of IL-2-induced pSTAT5 production were measured over half an hour, demonstrating a similar signal transduction in both groups. However, starting on the fourth day of incubation, daclizumab-treated T cells exhibited greater expansion driven by enhanced survival under maintained proliferation rate. A mathematical modeling study further suggested a more pronounced transmission of a secondary signal by IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ as the most plausible explanation for the observed effect.

To the best of our knowledge, direct evidence of differential induction of additional pathways by IL-2 through its two receptor forms is lacking. Given the aforementioned prominent evidence that abnormally high cytokine levels should enhance immune cell responsiveness, we hypothesize that the outcome of the experiment by Waters et al. might be caused by a similar biomechanically-driven reaction of immune cells to a high concentration of daclizumab. Notably, a similar effect of enhanced T cell survival despite a reduced proliferation rate was observed by Wang et al.⁵¹ during a 3-day treatment of T cells with 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of IL-10.

The results of our study suggest that the existence of two IL-2R forms can be explained by the suppressibility of signaling through only one of them. Notably, IL-15R, the evolutionary precursor of IL-2R, appeared in jawed vertebrates (a group including sharks) and has a three-unit structure similar to that of the high-affinity IL-2R $\alpha\beta\gamma$. The divergence of IL-15R and IL-2R occurred in bony fish, with IL-15 still requiring the relevant α subunit for signaling, and IL-2 gaining

the ability to signal through both three-unit and two-unit receptor forms¹⁶¹.

This evolutionary route suggests that the existence of a suppressible IL-2R form confers an evolutionary advantage. This advantage may stem from the suppression of naive T cell proliferation (which can be promoted by monocytes in presence of IL-2¹⁶²) during T cell recruitment to highly infected sites with elevated cytokine levels. The resulting alleviation of proliferative competition should further promote the expansion of antigen-experienced T cells expressing IL-2R $\alpha\beta\gamma$, thus enhancing the generation of effective responders under severe inflammation. A similar reasoning may also apply to NK cells, capable of developing antigen-specific memory¹⁶³.

Structures of cytokine–receptor complexes may govern differential signaling suppressibility

Several earlier studies demonstrated that a short pre-treatment¹⁹ of pre-activated human^{17,20} and murine^{18,19} T cells with TGF- β , as well as its paired co-administration^{17,18,20} with IL-2^{17,18} or IL-12^{19,20}, suppresses the signaling of these interleukins within 10-20 minutes by inhibiting JAK phosphorylation. The mechanisms behind these effects were not identified, with proposed explanations including TGF- β -induced activation of some phosphatase^{19,20} and allosteric effects¹⁹. Additionally, recent experimental data by Cheemalavagu et al.²¹ demonstrate decreased intensity of IL-10 signaling within the first 15 minutes of its co-administration with IL-6 in murine macrophages. Subsequent mathematical modeling reproduced this effect *in silico* under the assumption that IL-6-mediated transcription of SOCS1 inhibits phosphorylation of JAK1, associated with both IL-10R and IL-6R, in selective manner¹⁶⁴.

These hypotheses are not congruent with the signaling suppression pattern observed in our data, in particular with the effects mediated by cytokines with negligible signaling activity. Given the distinct stratification of cytokine-receptor complexes into suppressible and insuppressible groups, we hypothesize that the observed signaling suppression pattern arises from the differential sensitivities of membrane-embedded cytokine-receptor complexes to cell membrane tension. At a conceptual level, the specific structures of relevant receptors support our hypothesis.

IL-10 and IFN- γ receptor complexes are topologically similar, each forming a hexameric structure with a dimerized cytokine initiating signaling by engaging two separate dimerized receptor units^{165,166}. However, the IL-10 receptor complex has a nearly twice greater distance between these units, resulting in a significantly flatter profile compared to the IFN- γ receptor complex¹⁶⁶. This structural distinction suggests that IL-10R signaling may be more sensitive to increased membrane tension that tends to separate the receptor units and their associated JAK kinases.

Another hexameric receptor complex of IL-6 requires two ligand monomers for signaling¹⁶⁷. This feature may render its signaling more prone to disruption, as the dissociation of either monomer will also detach it from the signaling complex.

The structure of IFNAR is marked by the significant flexibility of its low-affinity subunit, enabling it to optimize binding with the cytokine while being embedded in a moderately dynamic membrane. This feature was demonstrated in the molecular dynamics study by Li et al.¹⁶⁸, where the investigators proposed that the ability to probe multiple conformations should allow for the regulation of IFNAR signaling. Consistent with this notion, there exist multiple IFN- α subtypes, all of which, along with IFN- β and three other IFNs, bind to IFNAR¹⁶⁹ inducing quantitatively different broad-range STAT signaling and leading to different downstream effects¹⁷⁰ and functional outcomes¹⁷¹. The intrinsic flexibility may also enable IFNAR to support and adjust its signaling in response to the changes in membrane tension, potentially explaining the selective suppression of certain axes, which emerges in our results.

IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ and both types of IL-4R are structurally similar, each consisting of two subunits. The binding affinity of IL-4 to its receptors is primarily governed by its interaction with IL-4R α , which is present in both types of IL-4R¹⁷². The dissociation constant for the binding of IL-4 and IL-4R α is $\sim 1.5 \cdot 10^{-10}$ M¹⁷³, while for the binding of IL-2 and IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ it is greater by nearly an order of magnitude¹⁷⁴. This difference may make IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ signaling less stable under elevated membrane tension compared to IL-4R signaling. The assembly of high-affinity IL-2R involves the IL-2R α subunit, which captures IL-2 and presents it to the other subunits¹⁵³. This assembly decreases the relevant dissociation constant by two orders of magnitude, possibly rendering IL-2 signaling effectively insuppressible.

Our theoretical reasoning is also supported by the growing recognition of membrane geometry and tension as the key modulators of T cell and B cell antigen receptor signaling¹⁷⁵ and by the molecular dynamics modeling study of Simunovic and Voth¹⁷⁶, showing that elevated tension can inhibit interactions between certain membrane-bound proteins, impairing their assembly and reducing the lifetime of dimers. These results thus support the plausibility of a similar cell membrane involvement in the regulation of signaling of cytokines.

Non-specific cytokine binding is the most plausible crucial driver of signaling suppression

Given the observed striking ability of cytokines with negligible signaling to suppress the signaling of other cytokines, we hypothesize that the cell membrane alterations, supposedly underlying this effect, are mainly induced by the non-specific binding of cytokines to membrane-associated molecules. Experimental studies show that the number of cytokine molecules non-specifically bound to immune cells initially grows linearly with increasing cytokine concentration^{177,178}. Weber-Nordt et al.¹⁷⁹ reported that non-specific binding of IL-10 in their experiments accounted for 2-3% of its total binding to murine B cells and Th1 cells, while saturation of IL-10R on $9 \cdot 10^6$ cells of each type was achieved under administration of 7.5 ng

of IL-10, of which 0.12 ng was bound. Given the IL-10 homodimer mass of ~ 37 kDa¹⁸⁰, the linear extrapolation of these values to our setting (50 ng of IL-10 per $0.5 \cdot 10^6$ cells) suggests that an average immune cell during our relevant experiments was non-specifically bound to ~ 260 -780 IL-10 molecules, and/or to a comparable number of other cytokine molecules, which is thus presumably sufficient to impact cell membrane dynamics.

Notably, all of the interleukins used in our experiments, along with IFN- γ and TGF- β , can bind either to heparan sulfate¹⁸¹⁻¹⁸⁵ or heparin^{186,187}, which infers that they interact with heparan sulfate proteoglycans (HSPGs)¹⁸⁸, the components of the glycocalyx layer covering the cell surfaces. HSPGs were shown to have profound effects on cell activity even at low expression levels¹⁸⁹, in particular, by promoting antigen presentation to T cells¹⁹⁰, regulating activation of T cells and NK cells¹⁹¹⁻¹⁹³, and controlling antigen uptake in B cells¹⁹⁰.

Notably, the cytoplasmic domains of syndecans, the members of HSPG family, are associated with the actin cortex and induce its rearrangement upon binding of syndecans to extracellular matrix¹⁹⁴. Syndecans can activate the signaling pathway that regulates actin polymerization within minutes even in response to soluble fibronectin fragments¹⁹⁵. It is therefore plausible that syndecan binding to cytokine molecules may as well trigger actin polymerization. Thus, syndecans may represent one of the key mediators for translating extracellular cytokine levels into mechanical effects.

Furthermore, syndecans were shown to induce the growth of microvilli¹⁹⁶, the finger-like protrusions facilitating lymphocyte interactions with antigens and other cells¹⁹⁷⁻¹⁹⁹ and contributing to up to a half of the cell surface area²⁰⁰. In line with our theoretical reasoning, Orbach et al. suggested that the deformations of microvilli may influence the organization of cytokine-receptor complexes and their activities²⁰¹. This suggestion can also be projected to the irregular ruffles of monocyte plasma membranes which, based on the estimates for macrophages, may constitute 20-40% of their cell surface area²⁰².

Intriguingly, the assembly of the IFN- γ receptor complex was shown to be largely facilitated by heparan sulfate oligosaccharides pulling this cytokine towards the cell surface²⁰³. These active interactions may enhance cell membrane deformations induced by IFN- γ , explaining the observed correlation of the levels of IFN- γ /STAT1 signaling and IFN- γ -induced IL-10/STAT3 signaling suppression in some of our experimental settings.

In the absence of syndecan-induced actin polymerization, the binding of cytokines to HSPGs and other membrane-associated molecules can still contribute to the increase of cell membrane tension via elevation of the steric pressure arising from random collisions of crowded membrane-bound proteins, which was shown to be able to locally stretch and bend cell membranes regardless of the proteins' structure²⁰⁴. In particular, the increase of steric pressure may govern the observed suppression of IL-10/STAT3 signaling by IFN- α . IFN- α 2a (the subtype used in our study) has a minimal binding affinity to heparin, suggesting that it does not interact significantly with HSPGs¹⁷¹, however, the consistent JAK-STAT signaling of IFN- α across all considered cell types indicates that its receptors are ubiquitously expressed in them. Therefore, we hypothesize that for IFN- α the specific binding-related events accompanied by the significant flexibility of IFNAR¹⁶⁸ can drive bending and stretching of cell membranes and thus induce suppression of IL-10/STAT3 signaling, strong enough to compensate for the additional pSTAT3 induction by IFN- α .

The prominent sensitivity of immune cells to external cytokine levels can be explained by a positive feedback regulation for the amplification of membrane tension, which was demonstrated by Atcha et al.⁷⁶. Mechanical stretching of cell plasma membranes triggers the opening of Piezo1 channels, which are present in lymphocytes and monocytes²⁰⁵. In the open state, these channels allow intracellular influx of various cations, including Ca^{2+} ²⁰⁶. Among its effects, Ca^{2+} induces actin polymerization²⁰⁷, leading to the stiffening of cellular cortex²⁰⁸ as well as plasma membrane, which together form a composite cellular surface²⁰⁹, and thus further promoting Piezo1-mediated Ca^{2+} influx. The actin cortex has a strain-stress relationship displaying notable non-linear growth starting from only ~ 2 -3% extensional strain. This indicates that its stiffness, i.e., resistance to deformation, grows with the increase of applied stress, i.e., force per cross-sectional area²¹⁰. Therefore, while a moderate increase of cell surface tension may disrupt the signaling of the assembled cytokine-receptor complexes, significantly high tension should also additionally enhance cell surface stiffness, thus inhibiting the assembly of certain complexes, as these processes rely on local membrane deformation²¹¹.

The proposed set of hypotheses (Figure 5B) suggests that the extent of signaling suppression entailed by cytokines should depend on their size and shape, with larger and more structurally complex molecules expected to induce higher steric pressure and/or stronger syndecan-mediated actin polymerization. Intriguingly, our experimental data perfectly aligns with this reasoning, showing that large dimers with complex elongated shapes, IL-12 (with the mass of 70 kDa) and TGF- β (25 kDa), generally act as the most potent signaling suppressors despite the weak own signaling. In contrast, smaller and more compact monomers, IL-2 (15.5 kDa) and IL-4 (~ 15 kDa)¹⁸⁰ demonstrate notably weaker suppressive capabilities.

Potential implications for the immune system control

Overall, our theoretical reasoning highlights cell membrane as a potential major participant in the cytokine signaling processes, which enables rewiring of JAK-STAT signaling in lymphocytes and monocytes within a time frame of several minutes. Presumably, the differential sensitivity of cytokine receptors to membrane tension was shaped through gradual evolution, involving small changes in sensitivity and favoring the ones that optimize the overall immune response. Like

any evolutionary shaped mechanism, it is plausible that the selective signaling suppression machinery is prone to errors in certain individuals³², compromising the activation or deactivation of their immune systems. One of the drivers of such malfunction, and therefore a therapeutical target, may be cholesterol, with its content in a cell membrane significantly affecting its stiffness²¹².

It is possible that other types of immune cells also leverage the mechanisms of selective signaling suppression, which may also extend to other cytokine-receptor complexes. This notion aligns with the experimental results of Houk et al.²¹³, who demonstrated that membrane tension acts as a long-range signaling inhibitor in migrating neutrophils, and with the findings of Pazdrak et al.²¹⁴, who showed that 15-minute pre-treatment of eosinophils with TGF- β suppresses their IL-5 signaling. It is also possible that selective signaling suppression can extend to non-immune cells, broadening the potential applications of the modulation of cell membrane composition as a therapeutic strategy²¹⁵. This notion is supported by the experimental results of Weber-Nordt et al.¹⁷⁹, who showed that 24-hour lipopolysaccharide treatment of fibroblasts reduced the affinity of their IL-10 receptors by more than an order of magnitude.

We hypothesize that, despite being a powerful evolutionary adaptation, selective signaling suppression machinery has a significant drawback, associated with the possibility of a prolonged suppression of IL-10 and IL-6 signaling, creating optimal conditions for triggering the cytokine release syndrome. The strategies aimed at restoring the immunosuppressive signaling of IL-10, such as generating its high-affinity mutants^{166,216} and altering its shape and conformational transitions, can offer a promising approach to overcoming the hyporesponsiveness of immune cells to IL-10, and thereby alleviating cytokine storms. Such approaches would also address the lack of IL-10 efficacy in clinical settings for treating autoimmune and immune-mediated inflammatory diseases^{45,217}.

Materials and Methods

Peripheral blood samples were collected from donors at the City of Hope Blood Donor Center, following the protocols approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB 21368 and 19186). All donors were women with a mean age of 52.7 years. Blood was drawn into EDTA-treated tubes, and peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were isolated using Ficoll-Paque density gradient centrifugation (Cytiva, Marlborough, MA, USA), in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. The isolated PBMCs were then cryopreserved in a solution containing 10% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and fetal bovine serum (FBS).

Cell culture. Cryopreserved PBMCs were thawed and incubated overnight during 16 hours in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum and 1% penicillin-streptomycin-glutamine (PSG) under controlled conditions: 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cell counts and viability were assessed using a hemocytometer and the trypan blue exclusion method (Sigma-Aldrich). Following this, the cells were cultured in a 96-deep well plate at densities ranging from 0.5 to 1 × 10⁶ cells/mL in 200 μ L of fresh RPMI 1640 medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., MA, USA).

Cell signaling. After a resting period, PBMCs were cultured either untreated or stimulated at 37°C for 15 minutes with 50 ng/mL of IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-10, IL-12, IFN- γ , or TGF- β , or 1000 IU/mL of IFN- α 2a (PeproTech, Rocky Hill, NJ, USA), added to cultures using multi-channel pipette. The cells were then fixed with 25 μ L 1.5% paraformaldehyde (PFA) for 10 minutes at room temperature. Following fixation, the cells were washed with 1x PBS and permeabilized using 500 μ L of ice-cold 100% methanol. The methanol-fixed cells were subsequently stored at -80°C. Prior to antibody staining, the cells were washed three times with staining buffer (PBS supplemented with 1% FBS).

Phospho-flow cytometry was conducted using the following antibodies: Percp-Cy5.5 (clone 4a) for pSTAT1, AF488 (clone 4/P-Stat3) for pSTAT3, AF647 (clone 38/P-Stat4) for pSTAT4, STAT5-PE-Cy7 (clone 47), V450 (clone 18/P-Stat6) for pSTAT6, BV570 (clone UCHT1) for CD3, BUV563 (clone SK3) for CD4, BUV805 (clone SK1) for CD8, APC-Cy7 (clone HCD14) for CD14, BUV737 (clone 3G8) for CD16, AF700 (clone H1) for CD20, BV786 (clone L128) for CD27, BUV395 (clone HI100) for CD45RA, PE-CF594 (clone 259D/C7) for Foxp3. Antibody dilutions were prepared following the manufacturer's guidelines and adjusted for optimal staining in preliminary experiments. Incubation was performed for 45 minutes at room temperature. All antibodies were obtained from BioLegend (San Diego, CA, USA) and BD Biosciences (Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA).

Data acquisition and gating strategy. The stained cells were analyzed using a Cytex Aurora flow cytometer equipped with lasers operating at 355 nm, 405 nm, 488 nm, 561 nm, and 640 nm. Compensation settings were determined using single-stain controls and a negative control. Data acquisition occurred at a rate of 1,000 events per second, with each sample collecting between 50,000 and 100,000 events. Gating strategies for identifying cell populations are provided in supplementary materials (Figure S7).

The following cell types and subtypes were classified: T cells (CD3+), helper T cells (CD4+), cytotoxic T cells (CD8+), naive CD4+ T cells (CD4+CD45RA+CD27+), naive CD8+ T cells (CD8+CD45RA+CD27+), central memory CD4+ T cells (CD4+CD45RA-CD27+), central memory CD8+ T cells (CD8+CD45RA-CD27+), effector memory CD4+ T cells (CD4+CD45RA-CD27-), effector memory CD8+ T cells (CD8+CD45RA-CD27-), CD4+ TEMRA cells (CD4+CD45RA+CD27-), CD8+ TEMRA cells (CD8+CD45RA+CD27-), resting Tregs (CD4+CD45RA+FOXP3^{low}), activated Tregs (CD4+CD45RA-FOXP3^{high}), non-suppressive Tregs (CD4+CD45RA-FOXP3^{low}), B cells (CD20+), mem-

ory B cells (CD20+CD27-), naive B cells (CD20+CD27+), NK cells (CD3-CD16+CD14-), monocytes (CD14+), classical monocytes (CD14+CD16-), and non-classical monocytes (CD14+CD16+).

Mathematical methods. For evaluation of Cumulative Shift Index for a pair of cell groups a and b , $\text{CSI}(a \rightarrow b)$, we relied on rank-biserial correlation, which is a method to report the effect size for the Mann–Whitney U test. For its calculation, all the cells from both groups are sorted and ranked, with rank 1 assigned to the cell with the lowest level of pSTAT of interest, and the rank equal to the total number of cells in two groups $n_a + n_b$ assigned to the cell with the highest level of that pSTAT. Then, Mann-Whitney U statistic for the group b is calculated as:

$$U_b = n_a \cdot n_b + \frac{n_b \cdot (n_b + 1)}{2} - R_b,$$

where R_b is the sum of ranks of elements in group b , and the first two terms represent its maximal possible value. Cumulative Shift Index is obtained by the normalization of U_b :

$$\text{CSI}(a \rightarrow b) = 1 - \frac{2 \cdot U_b}{n_a \cdot n_b},$$

so that it can take values from -1 to 1. As follows from this definition, $\text{CSI}(a \rightarrow b) = -\text{CSI}(b \rightarrow a)$.

For estimation of the Level of Suppression of the action of cytokine a under simultaneous application of cytokine b , $\text{LoS}(a|b)$, we use the formula

$$\text{LoS}(a|b) = -\frac{\text{CSI}(a \rightarrow ab)}{\text{CSI}(Base \rightarrow a)},$$

where $Base$, a , and ab represent the groups of untreated cells, cells treated only with cytokine a , and cells treated with both cytokines, respectively. Under this definition, a suppression that brings the distribution of pSTAT of interest within cells treated by two cytokines close to its basal distribution yields $\text{LoS}(a|b)$ close to 1. For demonstration of the results, unless otherwise indicated, for individual cytokine administration we retain only the cases where $|\text{CSI}(Base \rightarrow a)| \geq 0.1$ with corresponding p-value estimated by the Mann–Whitney U test being $p < 0.001$, and for paired cytokine administration we retain only the cases where $\text{CSI}(Base \rightarrow a) \geq 0.1$ and $-\text{CSI}(a \rightarrow ab) \geq 0.05$ with both corresponding p-values being $p < 0.001$.

To ensure a balanced representation of each donor’s cells for the aggregate analysis, an equal number of cells per donor were selected randomly for each experimental setting. This selection was based on the minimum number of relevant cells available from any single donor for each experimental condition, involving the same cell type and the same cytokine application. Donor F67’s cells were excluded from the aggregate analyses, as they exhibited significantly lower basal pSTAT levels compared to other donors’ cells, potentially due to an underlying disease. For correlation analysis (Figure 4) and individual donor analyses, provided in the supplementary figures, all available cells from each donor were included.

Code implementation. The computational codes were implemented in Wolfram Mathematica, version 14.1, and are provided in the supplementary files (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15330718>), along with the raw experimental data, processed data arrays, and distribution plots for each of the experimental settings and correlation analysis. The provided data and codes ensure the reproducibility of the results, and also allow performing aggregate analyses with a random selection of an equal number of cells from each donor across all experimental settings.

Disclosure of Potential Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest.

Authors’ Contributions

P.P.L., A.S.R., S.B., and R.R. conceived the project. P.P.L., A.S.R., and R.R. obtained the funding. P.P.L., A.S.R., S.B., R.R., and M.K. designed the experiments. A.S.R. and P.P.L. supervised the project. J.R.L.J. performed the experiments. M.K. analyzed the data, revealed the systematic signaling suppression, and performed all the computational and theoretical work. A.S.R. and S.B. supervised the computational work. M.K. drafted the first version of the manuscript with input from A.S.R. and P.P.L., and M.K. wrote the final version with feedback from all co-authors.

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